

TITLE

Models of care for people living with multimorbidity in primary care settings: a scoping review protocol of Primary Health Care-oriented approaches

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to the development or conduct of this scoping review.

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The funders had no role in the development of the protocol, including the formulation of the review questions, the design of the methodology, or the preparation of the manuscript.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This review is based solely on publicly available sources and does not involve human participants, identifiable personal data, or the collection of new empirical data. Therefore, ethical approval was not required.

INTRODUCTION

Multimorbidity, defined as the co-occurrence of at least two long-term health conditions in the same person (Skou et al., 2022; Valderas et al., 2009), is a growing global phenomenon, and represents one of the main challenges for current healthcare systems and society (McPhail, 2016; Skou et al., 2022). In community settings, the overall prevalence of multimorbidity in the adult population is around 37% and more than half of the adult population aged 60 and over live with multimorbidity (Chowdhury et al., 2023). Additionally, multimorbidity is associated with poorer quality of life, poorer health outcomes, higher health care utilisation and treatment costs, and higher socio-economic costs (McPhail, 2016; Skou et al., 2022; Tran et al., 2022). Therefore, the care of people living with multimorbidity poses complex clinical and organisational challenges.

In primary care settings, multimorbidity is notably prevalent, underscoring the need for effective management strategies (Carrasco-Ribelles et al., 2022; Ornstein et al., 2013; Soley-Bori et al., 2022). Therefore, various models of care have lately been developed and implemented within Primary Health Care (PHC) systems worldwide to address the people living with multimorbidity's health needs and priorities while also enhancing the efficiency of the healthcare system. These models have been examined and summarised in several recent reviews. Some reviews focus on these emerging models (Savitz & Bayliss, 2021), and others focus exclusively on PHC models (Aramrat et al., 2022; Frost et al., 2020; Longhini et al., 2022). Moreover, a range of reviews have analysed integrated care models (Boye et al., 2019; Dambha-Miller et al., 2021; Deschodt et al., 2020; Otieno et al., 2023; Rohwer et al., 2021, 2023; Tops et al., 2024), while others have examined the effects of specific roles or strategies, such as pharmacists (Davies et al., 2023), nurse practitioners-led primary care models (McMenamin et al., 2023), community-based interventions (Wasan et al., 2024), collaborative care interventions (Kappelin et al., 2022), care coordination interventions (Peart et al., 2020), interventions involving people in decision-making (Butterworth et al., 2020), and the use of information and communications technologies (Tahsin et al., 2023). Further reviews have focused on specific health outcomes (Eriksen et al., 2022) and on people with diabetes and multimorbidity (Brettel et al., 2021). However, these reviews either do not use specific frameworks for multimorbidity care models to describe them, or do not comprehensively examine all the domains and core elements of the models to determine whether they follow a PHC-oriented approach.

A model of care is a set of strategic decisions that specify “what” healthcare services are provided, “where” they are provided, and “how” they are provided (Davidson et al., 2006; World Health Organization, 2020). Considering the diverse approaches and populations encompassed by the concept of multimorbidity, using a comprehensive and specific framework to describe models of care for multimorbidity offers several advantages (Stokes et al., 2017). Firstly, it establishes a shared understanding among researchers and clinicians. Secondly, it enhances the description of existing models. Finally, it facilitates a more effective analysis of what interventions work for which populations. Furthermore, models of care have a significant impact on how well a health system operates. The ability of health systems to provide fair, person-centred, high-quality, and financially sustainable care may be compromised by fragmentation, particularly when service delivery platforms are organised around specific health conditions and population groups (Rajan et al., 2024). A key principle of PHC-oriented care models is the centrality of primary care in delivering comprehensive and integrated services. These models prioritise needs-based services throughout the life course, consider individuals’ preferences for accessing care, emphasise health promotion, prevention, and public health, and strengthen systems through a shift to ambulatory care and technological innovation (Rajan et al., 2024; World Health Organization, 2020). They also focus on first-contact accessibility and continuity of care coordination (World Health Organization, 2020). By guiding people through the health system, these models ensure high-quality primary care and promote effective linkages to timely acute care and robust referral systems at all levels. Moreover, they are closely aligned with the PHC components of "multisectoral policy and action" and "empowering people and communities" (Rajan et al., 2024; World Health Organization, 2020). In addition, PHC-oriented models explicitly aim to reduce inequities by guaranteeing universal access to essential services and tailoring care delivery to vulnerable and underserved populations.

Consequently, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the different models, of care for people living with multimorbidity developed in primary care settings, this scoping review aims to identify and describe the available information about their characteristics and examine their alignment with a PHC-oriented model of care. Additionally, we will use a specific multimorbidity framework to describe these models in terms of their foundations and core elements. A scoping review approach is particularly appropriate given the anticipated diversity and complexity of existing models and

interventions, and enables the identification of gaps in the current knowledge. This review may thereby serve as a precursor to future systematic reviews focused on specific components, strategies or outcomes.

This scoping review seeks to achieve its objectives by addressing the following questions:

- What models of care or programmes — or elements that could be integrated into models or programmes care — have been designed, developed, implemented or evaluated to provide healthcare services for people living with multimorbidity in primary care settings? What are their main characteristics?
- To what extent do these models, programmes or elements reflect or incorporate the key elements of PHC-oriented models of care? What dimensions of PHC-oriented approaches are evident in their design and implementation?
- What are the theoretical foundations and core components of the identified models, programmes or elements?

METHODS

This scoping review will be conducted according to the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2020). The reporting of the scoping review will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) (Tricco et al., 2018).

Eligibility criteria

We have defined the following eligibility criteria according to the JBI's approach:

Population

We will include studies whose population comprises people of any age living with multimorbidity. For the purposes of this review, multimorbidity is defined as the co-occurrence of two or more chronic or long-term health conditions within one person, where no condition is considered a known complication of another and no hierarchical relationship exists between them (Skou et al., 2022; Valderas et al., 2009). These health conditions will include: i) defined physical and mental health conditions such as diabetes or schizophrenia; ii) ongoing conditions such as learning disability; iii) symptom complexes such as frailty or chronic pain; iv) sensory impairment such as sight or hearing

loss, and v) alcohol and substance misuse (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2016).

Studies in which people with multimorbidity form a subpopulation within a broader sample will be included only if they report disaggregated data or findings specifically relevant to this subgroup.

We will also include studies where the population is not selected strictly based on a count of chronic conditions, but is either: (i) identified through characteristics commonly associated with multimorbidity (e.g. high healthcare use, clinical complexity), or (ii) explicitly described by the authors as comprising people with multimorbidity, even if specific conditions are not listed. In both cases, inclusion will depend on whether the described health profile aligns with the operational definition of multimorbidity adopted in this review and whether relevant or disaggregated data are reported for the target group.

We will exclude studies that:

- Focus on people with multimorbidity but report only on specific diseases without addressing the multimorbid context;
- Include only people with a single condition, without explicit consideration of multimorbidity;
- Are clearly framed around a single-disease perspective, even if participants have multiple conditions.

Concept

This review will include studies that describe, design, develop, implement, or evaluate care models or programmes aimed at people living with multimorbidity, as well as studies that analyse individual components or elements that could be integrated into such models or programmes.

Operational definitions:

Care models are defined as overarching designs for healthcare delivery, grounded in theoretical foundations, evidence-based practice and defined standards. They consist of structured components and guiding principles, and provide a framework for implementation and subsequent evaluation. Care models represent coordinated sets of interventions aimed at addressing specific conditions, populations, goals or settings, and

typically involve defined roles, responsibilities, and teamwork across healthcare providers (Davidson et al., 2006; Endalamaw et al., 2024; Stokes et al., 2017).

Care programmes refer to actual healthcare services, practices, or initiatives implemented in real-world settings. Programmes can range from small-scale interventions to population-level or regional care delivery approaches.

An element is any specific component or concept intended to contribute to care delivery. Elements may be part of a broader model or programme.

Studies will be included if they:

- Report on the design, development, implementation, or evaluation of structured care models or programmes guided by defined principles (e.g. integrated care, collaborative care, comprehensive care, person-centred care, chronic care model, guided care).
- Explore or assess specific elements that are, or could be, integrated into care models or programmes, including:
 - Clinical strategies (e.g. self-management support, holistic or preventive approaches, informed decision-making, mental health integration, guideline or protocol development, polypharmacy management);
 - Care organisation (e.g. case management, home care, social or community service integration, collaborative multidisciplinary work, visit formats, nurse-led services, group visits, 24/7 availability, trained navigator/coach models);
 - Support systems for care delivery (e.g. telehealth, risk stratification tools, professional development, training, telephone-based management, financing/payment models, health information systems, primary care networks).
- Examine perceptions, experiences, or attitudes of healthcare professionals, people receiving care, or caregivers regarding specific models, programmes, or elements of care.
- Present prediction studies that clearly connect their findings to the design, validation or evaluation of a care model, programme, or element — i.e. studies that propose or test practical applications that can be integrated into real-world care models for multimorbidity.

For inclusion, care models, programmes or elements must adopt a multimorbidity-oriented approach — that is, an approach that explicitly addresses the combined burden, prioritisation and complexity of people living with two or more chronic conditions, rather than focusing on the management of individual diseases.

Studies will be excluded if they:

- Focus solely on predicting service use without describing or evaluating any model, programme, or care element.
- Are limited to epidemiological analyses or pattern identification (e.g. multimorbidity clusters) without explicit linkage to a care model, programme, or element.
- Address only healthcare professionals', people receiving care's, or caregivers' general perceptions or attitudes about the health system, without reference to a specific model, programme, or care element.
- Do not include the design, development, implementation or evaluation of any care model, programme, or integrable element relevant to people with multimorbidity.

Context

This review will include studies conducted in primary care settings, defined as the part of the healthcare system that provides first-contact, accessible, continuous, comprehensive, and coordinated care that is person-centred (World Health Organization, 2020). As the cornerstone of the frontline services within PHC, primary care encompasses promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and palliative services throughout the life course (Rajan et al., 2024).

These services are typically provided in settings close to people's homes and, when individuals are unable to attend due to clinical or functional limitations, delivered within their homes. They may take place in a variety of settings such as general practitioner offices (individual or group practices), community health centres, polyclinics, nurse-led teams, mobile units, rural health posts, walk-in clinics, or other first-contact facilities (Rajan et al., 2024).

We will include studies reporting on models, programmes, or care elements implemented exclusively within primary care, or in combination with other levels of care

(such as hospital, specialist or social care), provided that primary care plays a central role, meaning it holds primary responsibility for coordinating and managing the person's care.

Studies will be excluded if primary care does not play a central role in the intervention, such as models delivered solely by hospitals (e.g. hospital-at-home programmes), or interventions focused on care transitions without primary care leadership or coordination.

Types of evidence sources

This scoping review will include a broad range of evidence sources to comprehensively capture the existing knowledge on the topic.

We will include:

- Original empirical studies using any methodological approach (quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods) regardless of whether they are fully published or available only as abstracts or conference proceedings;
- Review articles (systematic, scoping, realist, etc.) whose research questions are aligned with those of this review;
- Protocols of ongoing original studies, if they provide sufficient information about the design and objectives relevant to our eligibility criteria.

We will exclude:

- Protocols of review studies;
- Opinion pieces, editorials, and other non-empirical sources;
- Books and book chapters.

Reports in any language, publication date, and conducted in any geographical region will be considered.

Information sources

We will use the following databases and information sources to identify reports on the topic: (1) key international general healthcare databases, MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Scopus; and (2) study registers, Cochrane CENTRAL Register of Controlled Trials, and ISRCTN Registry. The included review studies will be used to identify any report that is not captured in searches. We will conduct complementary name-based searches in PubMed for each identified model, programme or element in order to retrieve additional relevant studies that may not have been captured by the structured search strategy.

Search strategy

An initial limited search of MEDLINE will be undertaken to identify reports on the topic. The text words in the titles and abstracts of relevant reports, as well as the index terms, will be used to develop a comprehensive search strategy. This search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will then be adapted for each included database and information source. No date or language restrictions will be applied.

The search strategy will be designed and implemented by one of the reviewers, who is an information scientist with expertise in information retrieval and the development of comprehensive and reproducible search strategies for evidence syntheses. Full search strategies for all databases, including all search terms and index terms used, will be documented and included as an appendix to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Data management and selection process

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into the Rayyan QCRI web application (Ouzzani et al. 2016), and duplicates will be removed. Following a pilot test, titles and abstracts will be independently screened by pairs of reviewers to assess them against the eligibility criteria. Potentially relevant reports will be retrieved in full. Each full-text report will then be assessed independently by two reviewers, working in pairs, using the eligibility criteria. Reviewers were linguistically competent to assess all the selected articles; in the case that any of the selected studies is written in a language in which the reviewers are not competent, the Google Translate tool will be used (Jackson et al., 2019; Pieper & Puljak, 2021). Reasons for excluding reports in full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported. Disagreements between reviewers will be resolved by consensus or, if necessary, by a third reviewer.

Data charting

Data charting will be conducted using a structured and standardised form developed specifically for this scoping review. The form has been designed to align with the review objectives, research questions, and inclusion criteria based on the PCC framework (Population, Concept, Context). A draft version, including all data fields, is included in this protocol (Annex 1).

To ensure clarity, completeness, and feasibility, the form will be piloted on a small sample of included studies. Based on the results of the pilot, the tool may be refined to

optimise data capture and reflect the evolving understanding of the evidence base. A companion guidance document will accompany the form, including operational definitions, coding instructions, and examples for each data field, to support a shared understanding among reviewers and ensure coherent and reproducible data charting.

The form will collect detailed information structured in four major sections: (1) descriptive features of the identified model, programme or element — including its name, type, approach, target population, health system context, care delivery structure and providers; (2) outcomes and aspects measured or assessed — based on the Core Outcome Set for Multimorbidity (COSmm) (Smith et al., 2018), which includes outcomes such as health-related quality of life, treatment burden, mental health, self-management, healthcare utilisation, and other domains relevant to people living with multimorbidity; (3) alignment with the core domains and key elements of PHC-oriented models of care, as defined by Rajan et al. (2024) in the WHO *Global Report on Primary Health Care* — including service selection and planning, service design, organisation and management, and community linkages and engagement; and (4) foundational characteristics and key elements based on the *Foundations Framework* proposed by Stokes et al. (2017), which includes the theoretical basis of the model, definition of the target population, clinical focus, organisation of care delivery, and support mechanisms for implementation.

Data will be grouped and analysed according to the model, programme or element described. When multiple studies refer to the same entity, their data will be consolidated to generate a comprehensive profile. This approach promotes consistency in data extraction, facilitates synthesis, and enables detailed mapping of characteristics, implementation strategies, and outcomes.

Each identified model, programme or element will be abstracted based on the included sources of evidence by one reviewer. A second reviewer will verify the extracted data and suggest modifications where needed. As an additional quality control step, a third reviewer will review all changes introduced by the second reviewer to ensure consistency and data accuracy. Although dual independent data extraction is generally recommended, this approach has been selected due to the expected size and complexity of the evidence base. In line with methodological guidance for large scoping reviews this process balances feasibility with rigour (Alexander et al., 2024).

Risk of bias in individual studies

This scoping review aims to map a body of literature comprehensively; therefore, in accordance with the guidelines for the development of scoping review proposed by the JBI (Peters et al., 2020, 2022), no critical appraisal or risk of bias assessment of the included studies will be performed.

Data analysis and presentation

A narrative summary of each included study will be displayed in tables. The data extracted will be grouped according to the different models of care, interventions or programmes identified. Frequency counts of data extraction items will be carried out. Qualitative information will be presented according to the deductive frameworks used in this scoping review. If, during the extraction and analysis stages of the scoping review, the authors find that this deductive approach is unsuitable for the extracted data and doubt its ability to provide a descriptive map of the available evidence, they will contemplate adopting an inductive approach (Pollock et al., 2023).

The review team will hold regular meetings throughout the extraction, analysis, and synthesis phases to ensure methodological consistency and collective decision-making.

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